

1 **SCIRT, a stem cell inhibitory transcript is regulated as a specific component of the TE**
2 **differentiation signature.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of stage
9 specific regulation of SCIRT, a stem cell inhibitory transcript, controlled as a specific component of the TE
10 differentiation signature. SCIRT changes seemed to function in lineage commitment in embryonic stem
11 cells of the human embryo.

12 Citations

13 1. Zagorac, S., de Giorgio, A., Dabrowska, A., Kalisz, M., Casas-Vila, N., Cathcart, P., Yiu, A.,
14 Ottaviani, S., Degani, N., Lombardo, Y. and Tweedie, A., 2021. SCIRT lncRNA restrains tumorigenesis by
15 opposing transcriptional programs of tumor-initiating cells. *Cancer Research*, 81(3), pp.580-593.